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/* (c).1993.11.13.John.C.McCarthy
   "S(n).h"
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Example Implementation of A Simple Algorithm to Calculate S(n),
The Smarandache Function:

Because there are more people familiar with C than with C++, this module has been written entirely in C (apart from "//" style comments). The module was compiled using Borland C++ version 3.1.

For efficiency, n is constrained to the limits of an unsigned long. Hence, $0 \leq n \leq 2^{32} - 1$ ($= 4,294,967,295$). ("^" represents exponentiation). Although catering for n of vast magnitude is possible, it imposes heavy storage and processing overheads. The range of an unsigned long therefore seems a reasonable compromise.

The algorithm depends on the most elementary properties of S(n):

1) Calculate the STANDARD FORM (SF) of n:

In SF: $n = +/- (p_1^{a_1}) * (p_2^{a_2}) * \dots * (p_r^{a_r})$ where $p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r$ denote the distinct prime factors of n and $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r$ are their respective multiplicities.

2) $S(n) = \max[S(p_1^{a_1}), \dots, S(p_r^{a_r})]$.

3) $S(p^a)$, where p is prime, is given by:

3.1) $a \leq p \implies S(p^a) = p^a$.

3.2) $a > p \implies S(p^a) = x < p^a$. In this case, fortunately rare, x is the smallest integer such that p appears as a factor in the list of all integers > 1 and $\leq x$ at least a times. Let the no. of times p appears as a factor in the list of all integers > 1 and $\leq y$ be $f(y, p)$. Then:

$f(y, p) = \sum [\text{int}(y/(p^i))] \text{ for } i > 0 \text{ while } y \geq (p^i)$.

Hence, x is the smallest integer such that $f(x, p) \geq a$.

Note that between successive integer multiples of p there are no integers which have p as a factor. The trick here is to look for the largest multiple of p (call it c), such that $f(p^*c, p) \leq a$ (so that $x = p^*c$, if $f(p^*c, p) = a$, else $x = p^*(c+1)$):

3.2.1) $c = a - 2$ (largest possibility for c since $f(p^*(a-1), p) \geq a$ when $a > p$ (Note: $f(p^*(a-1), p) = a$ is not sought for slight performance gain)).

3.2.2) $z = f(p^*c, p)$.

3.2.3) While($z > a$):

3.2.3.1) $d = \text{no. of times } p \text{ appears as a factor of } p^*c$
 $= (\text{no. of times } p \text{ appears as a factor of } c) + 1$.

3.2.3.2) $c = c - 1$ (next largest possibility for c).

3.2.3.3) $z = z - d$ ($= f(p^*c, p)$).

3.2.4) If($z < a$), $x = p^*(c+1)$.

3.2.5) Else $x = p^*c$.

To calculate the prime factors of all 32-bit n requires use only of primes $< (2^{16})$ (i.e. all primes expressible as an unsigned short integer). This is because any factor of n remaining after division of n by all its prime factors $< (2^{16})$ is simply a prime. Since there are only 6542 16-bit primes, the program first creates a list of these (which only takes about 4 seconds on my 20 MHz 386DX PC) so that they never have to be recalculated, thus saving much time.

*/

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#define PRIMES16 6542 // The number of 16-bit primes
#define MAX_SFK 9 /* max. distinct primes in the SF of n. The smallest
    number with more than 9 distinct primes is the product of the 10 smallest
    primes (= 6,469,693,230), which is substantially more than the largest
    integer expressible as an unsigned long. Hence, 9 distinct primes are
    more than ample.
*/

typedef unsigned long u_long;
typedef unsigned int u_int;
typedef enum {false, true} boolean;

struct SF_struct {
    int sfk; // no. of distinct primes
    u_long sfp[MAX_SFK]; // the distinct primes
    int sfa[MAX_SFK]; // respective multiplicities
};

extern u_int prime[PRIMES16+1]; // list of all 16-bit primes
// plus terminating zero.

void make_primes(void); // construct list of all 16-bit primes (prime[]).
// Must be called before calls to getSF() or S().
void getSF(u_long n, struct SF_struct *SF); // calc. SF of n and store in SF
u_long S(u_long n); // calc. S(n)
u_long Spa(u_long p, int a); // calc. S(p^a) where p is prime
int f(int x, int p); /* the number of times the prime p appears as a factor
    in the integers from 1 to x inclusive. This function is only called from
    Spa(p, a) when a>p with x=p*(a-2) (refer to item (3) of algorithm outline
    above). Max value of (a) occurs when p is a minimum, n is a maximum and
    (p^a)=n. So, (2^max(a))=max(n)=(2^32)-1. Hence max(a)<32. So, x<60
    when (a) is at its max. Max value of p (and x) occurs when a=p+1 and
    (p^a)=max(n). So, max(p)^(max(p)+1)=(2^32)-1. The upshot is that
    max(p)=9 when a=10. Hence, max(x)=72. This explains why it is safe for
    x, p and the return value of f(x,p) to be passed as ints.
*/

```